

TRANSACTIONS IN DATABASE MANAGAMENT SYSTEMS

Naim Nodira Abdulolovna

Senior teacher of the department convergence of digital technologies, Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

Ochilboyev Umidjon Ilxom o'g'li

Student of Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

Do'schanov Bekzod Davronbek o'g'li

Student of Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11219179>

The article is devoted to groups of sequential operations that are performed with databases, namely transactions.

Key words: databases, transactions, SQL language

When working with a database, there is a possibility of damaging or losing data. Let's give an example of transferring money from one account to another. To do this, you need to execute several SQL statements. If during their execution some hardware or software failure occurs, due to which one or more operators will not be executed, then it may happen that money will be withdrawn from one account, but will not go to another. To prevent this from happening, special measures are taken, the essence of which is that several SQL queries are defined as a single block called a transaction. In a transaction, either all of the statements execute successfully, or none of the statements execute, and the database returns to the initial state it was in before the transaction's statements began executing.

It follows that in this example, it is necessary to avoid a situation where one of the updates completes and the other does not, since in this case the database is in an inconsistent state. The transaction syntax is extremely simple and clear.

It begins with a BEGINTRANSACTION operation and ends with a COMMIT or ROLLBACK operation:

- The COMMIT (complete execution) statement signals the successful completion of the transaction. It tells the transaction manager that the logical unit of work has completed successfully, the database is (or will be after this statement is executed) in a consistent state, and all queries and updates performed by this transaction can now be committed, i.e., entered into database.

- The ROLLBACK statement is used when it is necessary to undo changes made by a transaction and restore the database to its previous state. The

operator informs the transaction manager that some kind of failure has occurred in the system, the database is in an inconsistent state and all queries and updates performed during this transaction should be rolled back, i.e. they should be canceled and the database returned to its original state. A transaction is characterized by four main properties, usually called ASID properties - Atomicity, Consistency, Insulation, Durability.

Atomicity. A transaction is a single logical unit, it is executed completely or not at all. If a transaction stops in the middle, the database must be saved in the state it was in before the transaction began.

Coherence (integrity). A transaction moves the database from one consistent (integer) state to another, also consistent. While a transaction is in progress, the database may be temporarily in an inconsistent state. Most database integrity rules are such that they simply cannot be broken by executing just one SQL statement. Such commands are grouped into a single transaction, which results in a new consistent state of the database. As a last resort, if the transaction fails to bring the database to the final integral state, it will return to the initial, also integral, state.

Insulation. In real information systems, tens of thousands of users can work at the same time, each of them running their own transactions. The isolation property means that all transactions are performed in isolation from each other. The greatest security is achieved with the highest level of transaction isolation, but this comes at the cost of reduced overall system performance. Even though the server may not be executing any transactions in parallel at any given time, the overall result of their joint work is guaranteed to be the same as it would be if they were executed sequentially. Concurrent transactions must not overlap each other and do not distort query results. This mode of server operation is called serial. Transactions are not performed in parallel, but sequentially.

Durability. Once a transaction has completed execution and is committed with a COMMIT statement, the result of its execution is guaranteed to be stored in the database. In case of any system failures, using server resources, you can restore all recorded transactions. The server, of course, does not guarantee recovery of uncommitted transactions. Thus, this article examined transactions, their syntax, namely the BEGINTRANSACTION, COMMIT, ROLLBACK operators, as well as 4 main properties of transactions (atomicity, consistency, isolation and durability).

References:

1. Наим Н.А., Modern trends in big data and data science, Сборник научных статей VII международной научно-практической конференции “Big data и анализ высокого уровня”. Минск– 2023. – С. 62-65.
2. Наим Н.А., Data analysis and processing, Сборник научных статей X международной научно-практической конференции “Big data и анализ высокого уровня”. Минск– 2024. – С. 161-163.

